

POLITICAL BASMACHISM AND ITS CURRENT SITUATION

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The wounds left by the 1916 uprising had not yet healed, the brutal atrocities committed by the Russians in suppressing that massive revolt had not been forgotten, and the national lessons drawn from the uprising had not faded from memory when the October Revolution took place. Turkestan, which had long been engaged in relentless struggles for freedom against Tsarist Russia, took advantage of Russia's internal weakness and openly raised the issue of its national independence and national statehood.

Having been deceived by Kerensky, the people of Turkestan utilized the time, circumstances, and the general situation in Russia. Shortly after the Bolsheviks came to power, they established their own national autonomous government. This national government was crushed by the Bolsheviks and came to an end on February 12, 1918. As a result, a mass uprising against Russia began in Turkestan.

The Bolsheviks labeled this uprising the "Basmachi movement." By giving it this name, they sought to discredit the people's rebellion and portray it to the world as insignificant. However, events did not unfold as they claimed. Although the people referred to their uprising as the "Begs' movement," they did not accept the name imposed by the enemy. Thus, in the history of our national liberation struggle, it became widely known as the Begs' movement or political Basmachism. Here, we will not dwell on the causes that gave rise to political Basmachism or its historical consequences, but rather focus on the lessons it taught us and its current state.

Political Basmachism in Turkestan was a movement expressing the will, aspirations, and determination of the people in their struggle for a national state. The popular movement that began in 1918 was the response of the Turkestani people to the Bolsheviks following the liquidation of our national government. Its primary goal was to liberate Turkestan from Russia, and this struggle has continued for 32 years. Although the 1916 movement did not achieve its aim, it left significant lessons for the comprehensive national movement of 1917. It should have demonstrated that Turkestan could not remain under Russian domination.

The 1916 uprising began as a response to Russia's oppressive and ruthless policy in Turkestan. Political Basmachism was primarily a national defensive and propaganda movement against Bolshevik Russia's oppression, aimed at preventing the country from becoming a secondary annexed territory of Russia.

The first to initiate political resistance was Ergash Qorboshi, the chief of police in Kokand. After defending Kokand from Bolshevik attacks and being forced to leave the city due to enemy invasion, he began gathering armed forces against the Bolsheviks.

When the Bolsheviks overthrew the government in Kokand, Mahmud Amin Beg (Madamin Beg), the chief of police in Margilan, was arrested. Subsequently, leaders such as Xolxo'ja from Osh, Parpi Qorboshi from Andijan, Muhitdin Beg from Navqand, Jonibek Qazi from Uzgend, Rahmonqul Beg from G'urtepa (Namangan), Omon Paxlivon and G'ajib Atar from Qizilravot, and Muhammad Shovot from Margilan fought against the Soviets, exhausting the weapons of Soviet offices. Ergash Qorboshi declared himself "Amir-ul-Muslimin," while Mahmud Amin Beg called himself "Lashkari Amir." On July 24, 1918, a congress was convened, and a provisional government was declared in Fergana.

Political Basmachism was not originally an organized national movement loyal to an established national government. It was a spontaneous wave initiated by the people against Russia. Unfortunately, the leaders of the national movement initially failed to achieve unity. The absence of a unified national organization and

supreme commander weakened the movement. This inability to establish solidarity—whether willingly or unwillingly—continued until the 1920s and worked to the advantage of the Soviets. However, the mistakes soon became evident. Under political pressure, it became clear that unless the movement united under a single national banner, it faced grave danger. Thus, by the late 1920s, national armed forces began to unite under one state flag. Sher Muhammad Beg played a significant role in this regard, and the history of the Turkestan national movement cannot be remembered without honoring such sons of the homeland.

On April 15, 1922, the Second Congress of Turkestan Muslims held in Samarkand defined the main objective of the political system in Turkestan. The national independence–political movement embodied the political, social, military, and moral demands of the Turkestan wars of independence. The content and future goals of the movement were clearly defined. The period of Enver Pasha in Turkestan marked one of the brightest stages of our struggle. Enver Pasha became a martyr in Turkestan—the homeland of the Turkic world—for our cause and for Turkism.

Although political resistance in Turkestan largely declined by the end of 1923, armed struggle continued in many parts of the country. This did not mean that political resistance had ended. Rather, it suggested that Red Russia had temporarily prevailed over Turkestan’s armored fighters. During the Tsarist period, Russian troops were stationed in Turkestan, and more than one million Russian colonists lived there. The Bolsheviks used them as instruments against national resistance. In 1916, more than 90,000 German and Austrian prisoners of war were settled in Turkestan. After the October Revolution, the Bolsheviks released them and sent them into the Red Army. The country was plundered by Russians, and immense sacrifices were made. Despite lacking modern arms and training, brave and courageous fighters continued to resist the Bolsheviks for generations.

From 1924 onward, the Bolsheviks intensified the Sovietization of Turkestan. Nevertheless, the Basmachi movement did not cease. According to Rahimboy

O‘g‘li, Chairman of the Presidium of the Tajik Soviet until 1937, “Basmachism in Central Asia was officially eliminated in 1935.” However, this “official” conclusion reflects only the Soviet perspective. In reality, there is ample evidence that Basmachism continued.

For example: The uprisings of 1935–36 in Suzak and Uchqo‘rg‘on; the revolt of the Uzbek National Division in Samarkand; the covert support of national forces within Soviet and Communist Party apparatuses by figures such as Akmal Ikromov, Fayzulla Khojaev, Ajtaqog‘li, Ataboy O‘g‘li, and Nusratulla Maksum until 1937–38; the flight of thousands of Turkestanis into deserts and mountains during mobilizations for the Red Army (1935–41), where they formed armed groups; attacks on Soviet officials and military commissars during 1941–45; uprisings in the Karakum during World War II and attacks on garrisons in Tashkent, Fergana, Alma-Ata, Osh, and Kogon—all demonstrate that political Basmachism persisted and that anti-Russian resistance intensified.

Even in recent times, uprisings in greater Turkestan (see issue No. 66 of *Milliy Turkistan*) reveal the current condition of political Basmachism. It must also be noted that after 1924 the Bolsheviks achieved certain limited successes. The NKVD apparatus was strengthened with powerful armed forces, and Russia’s military power increased. A terrifying system of terror was established, where even a single anti-Soviet word could result in years of imprisonment. Much of Turkestan’s present condition consists of prisons. From the outside, Turkestan may appear calm, but inside the country flames are burning. Turkestan’s children oppose Russian children, Turkestan’s women oppose Russian women, and elders oppose elders day and night. There is not a single day without clashes against Soviet authorities. Official Soviet publications themselves acknowledge anti-Soviet sentiment in Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan and discuss the absence of representatives at official meetings and even parliament (“*Izvestiya*,” April 26–28, 1950, Nos. 99–101). The uninterrupted struggle carried on for 32 years in

Turkestan proves that our claim to national independence is just and necessary, and that this reflects the true will and hope of our people. We have no doubt that political Basmachism in Turkestan will continue until national independence is achieved.

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